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Growth And Yield Response Of Pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis* Hook. F.) To Goat Urine Rates And Methods Of Application In South-South Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This particular study was carried out at the renowned Research and Teaching Facility (RTF) of the Faculty of Agriculture, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria. This case was compelled by the application of inorganic fertilizers to augment the soils for enhanced pumpkin production. The use of any of these inorganic materials poses an enormous danger to human beings as well as the agricultural ecosystem. Therefore, the aim of the study was to determine the growth and yield response of pumpkin to rated application of goat urine and the method of application. The study was done using split-split factorial (3 x 4) in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Over all, two main factors-rate- 0, 200kg/h, 300 kg/h and 400kg/h and method: ring, spot and double had 6 sub-factors. The measurements carried out which were done at interval of 2 weeks included number of leaves, number of branches, vine length, stem girth, leaf area, leaf area index and total leaf yield. Data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Variance(ANOVA) and Tukey HSD. A treatment of pumpkin dressed with goat urine gave the best results in growth and yield when applied at the rate of 400kg/h using the ring method. For farmers conducting research in specific study areas, it is advisable to apply goat urine at 400kg/h with the ring method for efficient pumpkin production.

Keywords: Goat, Urine, Rates, Methods, Pumpkin

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Telfairia occidentalis Hook. F. popularly referred to as pumpkin is a vegetable with both edible leaves and seeds. Pumpkin has great commercial value and so is in high demand amongst farmers (Odiaka et al 2008, Chukwudi and Agba 2014b). The seeds serve as a local condiment known as ogiri and are also used as a soup sweetener (Oyolu, 1998). The vegetable is an excellent source of vitamins and minerals and provides approximately; 20 percent protein, 18 percent fat and 20 percent vitamins and minerals (Ndor et al., 2013). Odiaka et al, (2001) reported that more than half (53 percent) of the composition of pumpkin is fat while 27 percent is crude protein. The extract of the leaves enhances the defense mechanism of the body (Eseyin et al, 2005). Akang et al (2010) noted that the oil from the seeds of pumpkin has lactating advantages and is greatly used by nursing mothers.

Even when farmers have access to inorganic fertilizers, which are harmful to health, soil, and the environment, they prefer using them due to their quick yields. This bounds reason why the health and wealth of the soil is neglected (Indabo and Abubaka, 2020). Little to no attention has been livestock waste, such as urine from goats, which to an extent is friendly when considering ecosystems reduces cost inexpensive, easy to get, and enhances the fertility of soil (Kapsiya et al., 2018).

Omotoso and Shittu (2007) noted growth parameters such as plant height, number of leaves, leaf area, root length, and number of branches for okra were recorded at their highest using an application rate of 300 kg/ha NPK. This supports the remarks of Babatola et al. (2002) who reported that increase in the levels of NPK 20:10:11 tend to boost the growth and yield of okra. They noted also that plant height, number of leaves, and number of branches showed a statically no significant difference between them.

Omotoso and Shittu (2007) noticed that the fresh weight of Okra leaves, roots, and stems treated with NPK 150 kg/ha had greater weights than those treated with NPK 150 kg/ha and 0. As for dry weight, only stem and root weight was significantly greater. No significant difference was observed for the dry fruit weight. This is in accordance with Obi et al. (2022) who also reported no significant increase in fresh and dry weight of okra with high rates of fertilizer application. Those with ring method of application showed significant difference in weight of leaves and fruits, dry fruit weight, and dry fruit weight. This corroborates with Olufolaji (2002) who reported the increase of area of leaf as well as fruit yield.

For the yield and its components like the number of fruits, their length, girth, fresh weight per plant and for the yield of fresh fruit per plant, Okra plants treated with 150 Kg/ha NPK gave the best results comparatively with 300 Kg/ha NPK to the control treatment. However, the highest values for the number of fruits, their length, width, weight and total fresh weight were obtained with the ring method of application. The ring method application did perform well receiving the highest number of leaves, plant height and branches. Omotoso and Shittu (2007) suggested that for best results in Okra cultivation, application of ring method and 150 Kg/ha NPK NPK fertilizer dosage should be utilized.

In a separate study, Adiaha and Agba (2016) acknowledged that the highest plant height of 36.30 cm with the ring method of application was achieved with 0.123 kg/ha NPK 15:15:15 while those with hole application, liquid add, control and were 77.67 cm, 77.30 cm, and 63.66 cm respectively. It was noted that applying 0.128 kg/ha resulted in winning for ring, hole, broadcasting and liquid adding methods. A significant difference was noted in comparison to the control methods which this report corroborates with Omotoso and Shittu's (2009) report who noted growth parameter increase with NPK fertilizer under ring method application on Okra.

In terms of the number of leaves, a similar trend was observed where the maximum number of leaves was recorded for maize treated with 0.128 kg/ha NPK using the ring method. Adiaha and Agba (2016) concluded that with regard to the growth performance of maize, it was evident that the NPK fertilizer rates and methods of application had an impact which indicated that the ring method of application was better than the control. The primary aim of the study is to evaluate the growth and yield response of pumpkin to different rates and application methods of goat urine.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The trial was carried out at the Research and Teaching Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture at Southern Delta University, Ozoro, in Delta State, Nigeria. Ozoro is located between Latitude 6 ° 30' 11" N and 6 ° 45' 11" N of the Equator and Longitude 5 ° 45' 11" E and 6 ° 13' 11" E of the Greenwich Meridian. Ozoro has a periodic downpour of 2500 – 3000 mm and a mean periodic temperature ranging from 28 – 30 °C.

3.2 Sources of Planting Accoutrements

Pumpkin capsules were bought from pumpkin growers in Ozoro.

3.3 Source of Animal Urine

Both goat and cow urine were bought from keepers or herders in Ozoro.

3.4 Experimental Design

The trial was a split-split (3 x 4) factorial laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications.

3.5 Soil and Urine Analysis

Soil samples from the experimental point were collected at a depth of 20 cm. The soil samples and beast urine were subjected to analysis for their chemical components and the nutritional composition.

3.6 Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data were collected at intervals of two weeks. The data collected included the number of leaves, which was determined by counting; the number of branches, also counted; the vine length, which was measured using a cadence rule from the base to the apical cub; and the plant girth, from using a Vernier caliper. The average leaf area in cm² was calculated as follows

$$\text{Leaf Area} = \frac{(L1 \times W1) + (L2 \times W2) + (L3 \times W3)}{3}$$

Where: L1 – 3 = length for the three readings

W1 – 3 = width for the three readings

(Silva et al., 1998)

$$\text{Leaf Area Index} = \frac{\text{Leaf Area}}{\text{Spacing}} = \frac{LA}{.5 \times .6} \text{ or } \frac{LA}{50 \times 60 \text{ cm}}$$

Leaf yield gathered by importing the samples using a sensitive scale, with results expressed in grams. Data collected were analyzed using ANOVA, and means were separated using Tukey's HSD. Leaf yield obtained by using sensitive scale was weigh in (grams).

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated using Tukey's HSD.

4.1.0 RESULTS

The results on study area soil chemical characteristics as shown in Table 1.0, indicated that the soil pH value was 4.33 when measured in 1:2 soil-to-water ratio (H₂O). Organic carbon was found to be 0.47%, while organic matter content was 1.32%.

The nitrogen content was 0.10 mg/kg, phosphorus was 4.67 mg/kg, and potassium (K) was 0.41 mg/kg. The levels of sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and iron (Fe) were measured at 0.40 mg/kg, 2.10 mg/kg, 1.00 mg/kg, and 0.19 mg/kg, respectively. Additionally, lead (Pb) was recorded at 0.03 ppm, zinc (Zn) at 0.24 ppm, and copper (Cu) at 0.24 ppm.

Table 1.0: Chemical properties of the soil of the study area.

Chemical Properties	Values
pH 1.2 (H ₂ O)	4.33
Oc (5%)	0.77
Om (%)	1.32
N (mg/kg)	0.10
P (mg/kg)	4.67
K (mg/kg)	0.41
Na (moi/kg)	0.40
Ca (moi/kg)	2.10
Mg (moi/kg)	1.00
Fe (ppm)	0.19
Zn (ppm)	0.24
Cu (ppm)	0.24
Pb (ppm)	0.03

The nitrogen (N) data showed values between 0.33 and 0.55% for compound goat and cow urine in the experiment as shown in Table 2.0. The results obtained from potassium (K) showed a range of 11.31 to 14.04 mg/L while the phosphorus values were observed between 7.53 to 8.84 mg/L. The magnesium values were within the limits of 0.86 to 1.02 mg/L while the sodium values ranged between 5.56 and 7.46 mg/L. For Calcium the data showed a range of 1.62 to 2.14 mg/L, magnesium was constant at 0.10 mg/L for both goat and cow urine. Iron concentration showed a span of values ranging between 0.16 to 0.20 mg/L. In addition, lead values ranged at 0.01-0.02 mg/L, zinc was at 0.23-0.25 mg/L, copper was at 0.17-0.20 mg/L.

Table 2.0: Composition of goat and cow urine

Parameters	Goat Urine	Cow Urine
Nitrogen %	0.33	0.55
Potassium %	14.04	11.31
Phosphorous %	8.84	7.53
Magnesium	1.02	0.86
Sodium	7.46	5.56
Calcium	2.14	1.62
Maganess	0.10	0.10
Iron	0.20	0.16
Lead	9.02	0.01
Zinc	0.25	0.23
Copper	0.17	0.20

According to Table 3.0, both the rates and methods of application of urine had an influence on the performance of pumpkin. The results were observed to range from 15 to 52.88, the ring method of application with regard to number of leaves (52.58) having the highest and the control treatment (15.00) having the least. Nonetheless, there was a clear difference among the treatments at 5% level of probability. For the rate, the results range from 15.00 to 58.44, and it was clear that the number of leaves was positively influenced by the rate of application. The highest number of leaves (58.44) was recorded at 400 kg/ha while the least (15.00) was observed at the control treatment. The 5% level of probability indicated significant differences among treatments.

Table 3.0: Number of levels of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application at 6 – 14 WATA

Sources of Urine	Methods of Application	6	8	10	12	14
	Double	20.00ab	34.33b	36.92abc	40.75b	45.00ab
Goat	Ring	20.92a	44.67a	43.92a	49.14a	52.58a
	Spot	18.83abc	27.75cd	30.33bc	33.67bcd	38.43b
Rate	Methods of Application					
	0	15.00def	21.56fgh	25.78cd	28.33fgh	31.00ef
	200kg/h	18.11cde	31.33cd	34.78bcd	36.78c-g	39.78dce
	300kg/h	20.69bc	38.56b	40.00abc	48.22ab	52.11ab
	400kg/h	25.89a	50.89a	47.67a	51.44a	58.44a

Means in the column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different using Turkey's HSD.

Number of branches of pumpkin using different methods and rates of application at 6 – 14 WATA.

The results in Table 4.0 which ranged from 1.75 to 4.08 indicated that pumpkins treated with the ring method of urine application had the highest number of branches (4.08), while the lowest number (1.75)

was recorded in the control treatment. There was a significant difference among the treatments at the 5% level of probability.

The results ranging from 1.33 to 9.67 depended on the rate of application. The findings revealed that pumpkins receiving goat urine at a rate of 400 kg/ha exhibited the highest number of branches (9.67), whereas the lowest number (1.33) was noted in the 0 kg/ha treatment. The various treatment displayed significant differences.

Table 4.0: Number of branches of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application at 6 – 14 WATA

Sources of Urine	Methods of Application	6	8	10	12	14
	Double	1.56abc	1.50bc	2.92ab	2.83ba	4.33cd
Goat	Ring	1.83abc	1.92ab	3.58a	6.17a	7.58a
	Spot	1.75abc	1.58bc	2.25bc	2.58c	4.08ed
Rate	0	1.33bc	1.11c	1.89cd	1.78d	1.98h
	200kg/h	1.67abc	1.44abc	3.22ab	2.89cd	3.39efg
	300kg/h	1.98abc	1.89abc	3.11abc	4.00bc	6.00cd
	400kg/h	2.00ab	2.22a	3.44a	6.78a	9.67a

Means in the column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different using Turkey's HSD.

Vine length of pumpkin using different methods and rates of application at 6 – 14 WATA.

Table 5.0 reveals that the methods and rates of application had a significant effect on the performance of pumpkin. The results ranged from 2.28 to 4.00, indicating that pumpkins treated with the ring method of application produced the longest vine length (4.00), while the shortest vine length (2.28) was recorded in the control treatment. Additionally, there were significant differences among the treatments at the 5% level of probability.

Regarding the rate of application, results ranged from 2.28 to 4.50. It was observed that pumpkins treated with goat urine at 400 kg/ha exhibited the highest vine length (4.50), while the lowest vine length (2.28) was noted in the control group. There were significant differences among the treatments at the 5% level of probability.

Table 5: Vine length of pumpkin using different methods and rates of application at 6 – 14 WATA.

Sources of Urine	Methods of Application	6	8	10	12	14
	Double	156.92ab	157.67abc	172.83abc	236.17bc	240.42bc
Goat	Ring	166.58ab	180.50ab	203.25a	289.58a	293.83a
	Spot	142.00abc	137.67c	161.67bc	217.50cd	225.75cd
Rate	0	90.44ab	110.44de	106.89cf	170.33cf	172.33ef
	200kg/h	149.44edef	139.89de	171.22bc	243.67bcd	246.67cd
	300kg/h	182.11abc	171.33bc	202.67ab	263.67ab	268.67abc
	400kg/h	198.67ab	212.78a	236.22a	313.33a	320.33a

Means in the column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different using Turkey's HSD.

Plant girth of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application at 6 – 14 WATA.

It was observed from Table 6.0 that the pumpkin which received ring method of application had the maximum plant girth measurement of 4.00 while the control registered the least measurement of 1.96. There were significant differences among the treatment. For rate of application the result ranged between 2.28 and 45.0 pumpkin that recorded goat urine at 400 kg/h had the significant increment of 4.50 measurement of plant girth while the least 2.28 measurement of plant girth was in the control. Differences were also notable between the treatments.

Table 6.0: Plant girth of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application.

Sources of Urine	Methods of Application	6	8	10	12	14
	Double	2.38bc	2.13d	3.25ab	3.33ab	3.83ab
Goat	Ring	2.63b	2.27cd	3.50a	3.75a	4.33a
	Spot	1.96cde	2.19d	2.92abc	3.42ab	4.00ab
Rate	0	2.23d	1.93d	2.67cdef	3.22abc	3.72bcde
	200kg/h	2.23dc	2.13cd	3.00abcde	3.44ab	3.94abcd
	300kg/h	2.23d	2.27cd	3.44abc	3.5ab	4.06abc
	400kg/h	2.50cd	2.46bad	3.78a	3.78a	4.50a

Means in the column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different using Turkey's HSD.

Yield parameters of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application at 6-14WATA.

Table 7.0 which revealed the yield parameters of pumpkin using different methods and rate of application had result ranging between 2733.4 – 5093.48. Pumpkin that recorded goat urine using ring method had the highest (57093.48) leaf area while the least (2733.4) was recorded for control. For leaf area index, the result ranges between 9.19 – 16.98. Pumpkin that received goat urine through ring method had the highest (16.98) leaf area index while the least (9.19) was recorded for control. As for the leaf yield, it also followed the same trend of ring method of application giving the highest (1.15) while least (0.28) leaf yield was recorded in the control.

There was significant difference among the treatment throughout the experimental period. For rate of application also had effect on production of pumpkin. The result ranges between 1849.911 – 6012.32. The result shows that pumpkin that received goat urine at 400kg/h had the highest (6012.32) leaf area while the least (1849.911) was recorded for control. For leaf area index, the result ranges between the result 6.17 – 20.0 also revealed that pumpkin that received goat urine at 400 kg/h of application had the highest (20.04) leaf area index while the least (6.17) was recorded for the control. For leaf yield, the result also shows that pumpkin that received goat urine at 400 kg/h had the highest (1.47) leaf yield while the least (0.28) leaf yield was recorded for control. However, there was significant difference among the treatment throughout the study.

Table 7.0: Yield parameters of pumpkin using different methods and rates of application at 6 – 14 WATA.

Sources of Urine	Methods of Application	Leaf Area cm ²	Leaf Area Index	Leaf Yield (th)
	Double	3668.30b	12.23b	0.63ab
Goat	Ring	5093.48a	16.98a	1.15a
	Spot	2733.24cd	9.11cd	0.86ab
Rate	0	1849.911fg	6.17fg	0.28d
	200kg/h	2972.02de	9.91de	0.59bcd
	300kg/h	4492.44b	14.97b	1.17abc
	00kg/h	6012.32a	20.04a	1.47a

4.2.0 DISCUSSION

The methods and rate of goat urine had great influences on the parameters such as number of leaves, number of branches, vine length, plant girth, leaf area, leaf area index and leaf yield. This findings agreed with Omotoso and Shittu (2007) who reported that okra dressed with 300 kg/h of goat manure had the highest number of leaves, plant height, leaf area, number of branches and root length. This report also is in agreement with Babatola et al., (2002) who observed that increasing level of NPK 20:10:10 was observed to increase growth and yield of okra.

This finding also in-line with Kolawole and Agbosanio (2018), stated that cucumber dressed with goat manure at 400 kg/h + nitrogen gave the highest number of leaves. They also observed that there were significant differences among the treatments at 5% level of probability. This result is also in agreement with (Hamma, et al., 2012), who observed highest number of leaves in cucumber dressed with 12 t/h of goat manure while the least number of leaves was recorded in control.

For methods of application, the finding agreed with Omotoso and Shittu (2007), who reported that okra that received ring method of application had significant difference of leaf fresh weight, dry weight and fruit dry weight.

This finding also agreed with Adiaha and Agba (2016), who observed that maize dressed with ring method of application gave the highest number of leaves. This finding corroborate the findings of Obi et al., (2000), who reported that okra that received ring method of application had significant difference at leaf fresh weight, dry weight and fruit dry weight. This also harmonized with Olufolaji (2002) who stated that an increase in leaf area and fruit yield. For rate of application the finding collaborates with Jokopurnomo and Andrani (2021) who reported that tomato dressed with goat manure + nitrogen gave the highest leaf area. However, there was no significant difference among the treatments. They also observed that fruit weight followed the same trend of goat manure at 400 kg/h + nitrogen having the highest fruit weight. Adiaha and Agba (2016) observed that NPK fertilizer rates and method of application influences the growth performance of maize and that ring method of application is more efficient compared with other treatments.

5. CONCLUSION

Goat urine rates and methods of application had great influence on the growth parameters and yield component of pumpkin. Pumpkin dressed with goat urine at 400 kg/h using ring method gave the highest performance in terms of number of leaves, number of branches, vine length, plant girth, leaf area, leaf area index and leaf yield throughout the experimental period. It is therefore recommended that farmers in the study area should use goat urine at 400 kg/h and ring method of application for the cultivation of pumpkin to maximize profit.

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